

Tourist Zones, Their Types and Economic-Social Significance

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Abstract: In this article, on the example of the countries of the world, the concept of a tourist zone, its types, legal foundations, organizational and economic mechanisms, advantages, positive and negative aspects in the development of the territory, the management system are considered.

Keywords: tourist zone, free tourist zone, small tourist zone, special tourist zone, artificial authenticity, tourist look.

Introduction. In the modern world of tourism, tourist zones are considered as a factor that rapidly develops the industry and ensures economic and social stability. Therefore, countries of the world are organizing tourist zones in tourist areas. This trend is also observed in our country. In particular, within the framework of the 35th goal of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the construction of additional tourist zones and recreation centers in Zomin, Forish, Bakhmal districts and the Aydar-Arnasoy lake system, 300 implementation of projects worth million US dollars, creation of 25,000 jobs" [1].

Analysis of literature on the topic. N.S. Kudryavtsev, J.G. Trabskaya, L.V. According to Khoreva, the tourist zone is a certain part of the most sought-after destination among tourists, which includes the main attractions leading to the national and international tourist markets [2].

A.V. And Lebedev, "located in one or more regions and providing conditions for establishing communication between the components of the tourism industry, ensuring the stable and rapid development of a certain region, satisfying the needs of citizens for recreation tourism complex" is called a tourist zone [3].

S.A. Stepanova defines the tourist zone as "limited to one or several regions and formed by the high density of the displayed objects, the type characteristics of the area, the presence of a developed infrastructure component, economic potential, the offer of tourist services based on favorable natural and climatic factors, the high level of transport use, as well as tourism an area with the possibility of introducing tourism services to external and internal development programs" [4].

N.G. Sannikova emphasizes that the tourist zone serves to develop tourism, provide a favorable investment environment, and create a competitive tourist product [5].

If we look at the theoretical approaches to the concept of "tourist zone" in foreign literature, the term "tourist zone" was first proposed by Eric Cohen in his work "Toward the Sociology of International Tourism" and he formulated the following thesis: "Mass tourists" feel the safety of the microenvironment at the same time, they want to feel the freshness of the macro environment of the destination. It is comfortable for them, it consists of hotels and familiar food - that is, it forms a special "zone" around them that they rarely leave [6]. Later, the definition of "tourist zone" was proposed to emphasize the importance of the touristic component in the interpretation of this term.

Dennis Judd calls tourist zones "islands of peace" that provide a sense of "security, protection and comfort" to the traveler, often radically different from the surrounding urban socio-cultural "landscape"[7].

In general, a tourist zone is a certain area that does not have clear boundaries, but has common specific tourist resources that can generate sustainable interest in tourists [8].

Research methodology. In the process of research, the types of tourist zones, the development of their infrastructure, the goals and tasks and directions of the state policy on the organization of tourist zones, the dialectical and systematic approach, comparative and comparative analysis methods were used by studying the opinion of experts and foreign experience in this regard. .

Analysis and results. Development of inbound tourism and domestic tourism, tourist industry, which has certain boundaries and has one or more tourist resources (natural, historical, socio-cultural, medical and health facilities, as well as other facilities that can satisfy the needs of tourists and excursionists) , the territory established for the purpose of protection of tourist resources and their rational use is a tourist zone[9].

Tourist zones are organized according to the proposal of state bodies and other organizations, as well as legal and natural persons carrying out business activities.

Tourist zones are organized at the national or local level. Tourist zones at the republican level are established on the basis of the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers, and tourist zones at the local level are established on the basis of the decisions of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city governments in agreement with the competent state body.

When determining tourist zones, the presence of tourist resources in them, as well as the potential opportunities for the development of tourism types of these areas are taken into account.

The owners and (or) owners of the tourist industry objects under construction, when tourist resources are being built in the territories of the tourist zones, as well as when using them, it is assumed that these objects will be integrated with the existing local socio-economic, historical, scientific, artistic, cultural environment or other organizational-purpose environment and infrastructure environment. must keep.

When organizing and implementing their activities in the tourist zones, the subjects of the tourism sector must ensure a careful attitude towards the natural environment, objects of cultural heritage and protected natural areas.

Tourist activities carried out in tourist zones and other activities not prohibited by law should not interfere with the goals of establishing tourist zones.

The following types of tourist zones can be established in order to comprehensively develop tourism and maintain tourist resources at the appropriate level, increase the tourist potential of the respective area, as well as encourage the attraction of investments in their development:

Figure 1. Types of tourist zones

Source: "On Tourism" of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the author. Prepared on the basis of the law

"About tourism" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, what kind of regions these tourist zones are, and their other possibilities. Article 18 of the law is duly defined.

Figure 2. Definition of types of tourist zones

Source: "On Tourism" of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the author. Prepared on the basis of the law

As a result of this law, a number of tourist zones were established in the regions. In particular, they include the free tourist zone "Chorvoq" in the Tashkent region, the tourist-recreational zone "Zomin" in the Jizzakh region, the small tourist zones "Shavot" in Urganch, and "Govuk kol" in Khiva. We will study the international practice in order to effectively launch the activities of these tourist zones.

In international practice, a "tourist zone" is defined as a place with a developed tourist infrastructure that attracts tourists. The value of this tourist zone is directly present today in scientific research and tourism practice [10]. Accordingly, tourist zones are called "central" and "peripheral" tourist zones.

"Central" tourist areas are crowded with tourists, while "peripheral" tourist areas do not attract enough tourists. But such zones can stimulate the redistribution of tourist flows and reduce the negative impact of tourism on the main tourist attractions.

One of the important features of the tourist zone can be called "artificial authenticity". The term "artificial authenticity" was first coined by Dean McConnell in 1973, which may not be true, but fits perfectly with the idea of tourists [11]. The issue of authenticity in tourism is the subject of many debates, but we can conclude that there is no single standard: the culture of a country is evolving and it is difficult to say which element is authentic and which element is false [12]. There are successful examples of introducing "tourist zone" and "artificial authenticity". For example, the Potaxo Indians of the Bana region of Brazil are actually made up of five different ethnic groups, encouraged by tourist agencies to "portray" a single "primitive" ethnic group. Despite the loss of individual identity of each ethnic group, there was a "Cultural Revival of Potaxo" and Indians gained additional social status in the region. It also inspired the development of the village of Alter de Chalo in the Brazilian Amazon, where a combination of local legends created a common village that served as the basis for the Saire festival. More than 6 thousand people will visit this festival. annually (the population of the village is about 4 thousand) and makes a great contribution to the economy of the region. It should be noted that despite the positive component, this festival leads to the separation of local residents and tourists, as more touristic infrastructure facilities appear in the center of the village, "pushing" the local population out of the center[13]. At the moment, the creation of a "tourist zone" in the Amazon is giving very positive results.

This example shows that along with the development of the tourist area, the development of the whole destination goes through several stages. The first is euphoria from the influx of tourists; the second is apathy, when the arrival of new tourists is taken for granted; the third is the stage of awareness, realizing that tourism brings not only benefits, but also negative consequences; the fourth stage is the stage of antagonism, in which a hostile attitude of the population towards tourists is formed, which is accompanied by attempts not only to reduce the damage caused by the flow of tourists, but also to reduce the tourist flows themselves; the fifth is the stage of peace, in which the population is forced to adapt to the changes resulting from the development of tourism [14].

Tourist areas are also often seen as divisive, preventing the tourist from gaining the necessary cultural experience or seeing the real city. For example, in studies conducted in Baltimore, scientists concluded that the development of a tourist zone only in the city center does not allow the development of other areas[15]; Studies in Atlanta have shown that in the central region, "the presence of a tourist zone and its active promotion on the Internet as a tourist center does not solve the problems of poverty and crime in the city, but increasingly separates tourists and local residents[16].

Based on the concept of the "tourist gaze"[17], which suggests that the most important places for a tourist are places that can be seen, photographed and taken away as impressions, it can be assumed that either at this level, all major cities have their own tourist areas, where the most famous and attractive objects of display are concentrated. Many European cities have well-known historic centers, which usually contain the most popular attractions. A study of urban tourism in Denmark showed that although tourists are increasingly visiting new areas of the city, the Copenhagen Destination Marketing Bureau is only promoting the historic center [18], which may have negative consequences in the long run.

Conclusions and suggestions. In order to organize tourist zones in the regions and increase their effectiveness, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- developed tourist infrastructure, cultural-historical monuments and other attractions, legislative framework and favorable political conditions, as well as the presence of interested parties in the development of tourism in this area.
- increasing the flow of foreign and local investment by turning tourist zones into partially or completely tax-free areas;
- creating a healthy competitive environment for business entities;
- encourage the creation of videos showing the attractiveness of tourist zones and actively promote them through social networks, the Internet and other mass media.

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